

**HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE UNITED STATES OF
AMERICA**

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Abstract: The United States, like all countries, has a unique history. We will think about the stages of development of this country, the events that this country went through before it became America. America is currently the 2nd largest and one of the most advanced countries.

Keywords: America, Washington, Adolf Hitler, George Washington, Texas, Democratc Party, Republican Party, Panama, Civil War.

The United States of America is a country in North America. Its capital is Washington, a member of the United Natons. The USA is surrounded by the Atlantc Ocean to the east, the Pacific Ocean to the west, and the Gulf of Mexico to the southeast. Administratvely, it is divided into 50 states and one federal district. The states of Alaska and Hawaii are located outside the main territory of the country. The Commonwealth of Puerto Rico, the Commonwealth of the Northern Mariana Islands, Guam, the Virgin Islands, and American Samoa also belong to the United States. Its area is 9.8 million km². Its populaton is more than 331 million people, and it is the third most populous country in the world.[1]

In ancient tmes, Indians and Eskimos lived in the territory of the present United States. Afer the discovery of America by Christopher Columbus in 1492, in the 16th century, Spain, France, England, Holland and Sweden began to occupy the empty lands in North America. In the middle of the 18th century, England

pushed out its main rivals and established its colonial rule in the eastern part of the continent. At the same time as land acquisition and settlement, the local population was exterminated and enslaved Negroes were imported en masse from Africa. During the North American War of Independence of 1775-83, on July 4, 1776, the United States of America was founded and declared a republic.[2] George Washington was elected the first president of the United States of America.

Industry and farming developed in the north of the country, and agriculture based on slavery in the south. The territory of the United States expanded rapidly due to the expulsion of Indian tribes in the West and the development of new lands. In 1803, West Louisiana was “purchased” from France, in 1819 Spain passed Florida, and in 1836 Texas was taken from Mexico. During the 19th century, territories of present-day California, Arizona, New Mexico, and Nevada, as well as parts of Colorado and Wyoming, were annexed. In the middle of the 19th century, a “two-party system” was formed in the USA.[3] Now the government is controlled alternately by the Democratic Party and the Republican Party. The conflict between the northern bourgeoisie and the southern planters led to the American Civil War of 1861-65, in which the northern states led by President Abraham Lincoln won. During the war, laws on land shares (1862) and abolition of slavery (1865) were passed. After the civil war, the country’s economy began to develop rapidly. In 1867, the United States bought Alaska and the Aleutian Islands from Tsarist Russia; At the end of the 19th century, it acquired the Philippines, Hawaii, Puerto Rico, etc., and in 1903, the Panama Canal Zone.[4] At the turn of two centuries, a new wave of immigration to the United States began. Most of the immigrants were from Southeast Europe. During the First World War (1914–1918), the United States was initially neutral, and in April 1917 moved on the side of the Entente. After the war, the US entered a period of economic growth. But soon the economic crisis (1929–1933) began, unemployment increased (in 1933 there were 17 million unemployed), enterprises collapsed, and production fell sharply. In the crisis, the administration of the

Democratic Party led by Franklin D. Roosevelt (1933-1945 US President) came to power.[5]

A number of socio-economic measures were implemented on his initiative, the so-called “new road” aimed to bring the United States out of the crisis. In 1941, after the Japanese attack on the American naval base at Pearl Harbor, the United States entered World War II and sided with the coalition against Adolf Hitler. The American armed forces were mainly involved in hostilities against Japan in the Pacific Ocean. In 1943, he sent troops to Italy. The USA participated in the international conferences of the Allies (Tehran in 1943, Crimea in 1945, Potsdam in 1945). Finally, on June 6, 1944, Great Britain and the United States opened a second front. In August 1945, by the order of Harry S. Truman (President of the USA in 1945-1953), atomic bombs were dropped on the Japanese cities of Hiroshima and Nagasaki; caused the killing of tens of thousands of civilians.[6] In 1950-1953, the United States participated in the Korean War, and in 1956-1975, it fought in Vietnam. Since 1945, the United States has been a member of the United Nations, the Organization of American States, and NATO.

What was to become American history began in a biological and cultural collision of Europeans, Native Americans, and Africans. Europeans initiated this contact and often dictated its terms. For Native Americans and Africans, American history began in disaster. Native Americans suffered heavily because of their isolation from the rest of the world. Europe, Africa, and Asia had been trading knowledge and technologies for centuries. Societies on all three continents had learned to use iron and kept herds of domestic animals. Europeans had acquired gunpowder, paper, and navigational equipment from the Chinese. Native Americans, on the other hand, had none of these. They were often helpless against European conquerors with horses, firearms, and — especially — armor and weapons. The most disastrous consequence of the long-term isolation of the Americas was biological. Asians, Africans, and Europeans had been exposed to one another’s diseases for millennia; by 1500 they had developed an Old World

immune system that partially protected them from most diseases. On average, Native Americans were bigger and healthier than the Europeans who first encountered them. But they were helpless against European and African diseases. Smallpox was the biggest killer, but illnesses such as measles and influenza also killed millions of people. The indigenous population of Mexico, for example, was more than 17 million when Cortés landed in 1519. By 1630 it had dropped to 750,000, largely as a result of disease. Scholars estimate that on average the population of a Native American people dropped 90 percent in the first century of contact. The worst wave of epidemics in human history cleared the way for European conquest. See also United States (People): Disease and Death in Early America.[7]

Europeans used the new lands as sources of precious metals and plantation agriculture. Both were complex operations that required labor in large, closely supervised groups. Attempts to enslave indigenous peoples failed, and attempts to force them into other forms of bound labor were slightly more successful but also failed because workers died of disease. Europeans turned to the African slave trade as a source of labor for the Americas. During the colonial periods of North and South America and the Caribbean, far more Africans than Europeans came to the New World. The slave trade brought wealth to some Europeans and some Africans, but the growth of the slave trade disrupted African political systems, turned slave raiding into full-scale war, and robbed many African societies of their young men. The European success story in the Americas was achieved at horrendous expense for the millions of Native Americans who died and for the millions of Africans who were enslaved.[8]

Beginning in 1519, Spain, Portugal, France, The Netherlands, and England established colonies in the Americas. Spain made a great mining and agricultural empire in Mexico, South America, and the Caribbean. Portugal created a slave-based agricultural colony in Brazil. In North America the French and Dutch established rudimentary European societies and, more importantly, elaborate, long-

term trading networks with the indigenous peoples. Among the European invaders of North America, only the English established colonies of agricultural settlers, whose interests in Native Americans was less about trade than about the acquisition of land. That fact would have huge implications in the long struggle for control of North America.[9]

Spain was the first European nation to colonize America. Cortés invaded Mexico and (with the help of smallpox and other Native Americans) defeated the Aztec Empire between 1519 and 1521. By 1533 Pizarro had conquered the Incas of Peru. Both civilizations possessed artifacts made of precious metals, and the Spanish searched for rumored piles of gold and silver. They sent expeditions under Hernando de Soto, Francisco Vásquez de Coronado, and Álvar Núñez Cabeza de Vaca as far north as what is now Kansas and Colorado. They were looking for cities made of gold and did not find them. But in 1545 they did discover silver at Potosí, in what is now Bolivia, and in Mexico around the same time. New World gold and silver mines were the base of Spanish wealth and power for the next hundred years.

Shortly after the conquests, Catholic missionaries — Jesuits until 1571, Franciscans and Dominicans after that — attempted to convert Native Americans to Christianity. They established missions not only at the centers of the new empire but also in New Mexico and Florida. Spanish Jesuits even built a short-lived mission outpost in Virginia. After defeating indigenous peoples, Spanish conquerors established a system of forced labor called *encomienda*. However, Spanish governmental and religious officials disliked the brutality of this system. As time passed, Spanish settlers claimed land rather than labor, establishing large estates called *haciendas*. By the time French, Dutch, Swedish, and English colonists began arriving in the New World in the early 17th century, the Spanish colonies in New Spain (Mexico), New Granada (Colombia), and the Caribbean were nearly 100 years old. The colonies were a source of power for Spain, and a source of jealousy from other European nations.[10]

The Wars for North America, 1689–1763, Seventeenth-century colonists fought wars with the coastal Native American peoples upon whom they had intruded. Eighteenth-century colonial wars, in contrast, usually began in Europe, and they pitted the English colonies against French and Spanish empires in North America. These empires posed a number of problems for English colonists. Spanish Florida offered refuge to runaway slaves from the southeastern colonies. The French built an interior arc of settlements from Québec to New Orleans; they also made trading agreements with Native Americans. The French trading empire impeded the expansion of English settlements, and the strength of the French and their Native American allies was a constant concern to the British and to American settlers. The English and French fought frequently: in King William’s War (1689–1697; known in Europe as the War of the League of Augsburg), in Queen Anne’s War (1702–1713; the War of the Spanish Succession), in King George’s War (1744–1748; War of the Austrian Succession), and in the French and Indian War (the Seven Years’ War), which began in America in 1754 and ended in Europe in 1763. In all of these wars, the French had the assistance of most Native Americans of the interior. The American Revolution. In 1776 the prospects for American victory seemed small. Britain had a population more than three times that of the colonies, and the British army was large, well-trained, and experienced. The Americans, on the other hand, had undisciplined militia and only the beginnings of a regular army or even a government. But Americans had powerful advantages that in the end were decisive. They fought on their own territory, and in order to win they did not have to defeat the British but only to convince the British that the colonists could not be defeated. The British fought in a huge, hostile territory. They could occupy the cities and control the land on which their army stood, but they could not subdue the American colonists. Two decisive battles of the war — Saratoga and Yorktown — are cases in point. At Saratoga, New York, a British army descending on the Hudson Valley from Canada outran its supply lines, became tangled in the wilderness, and was surrounded by Americans. The

Americans defeated a British detachment that was foraging for food near Bennington, Vermont, then attacked the main body of the British army at Saratoga. The British surrendered an army of about 5,800 (see Battles of Saratoga).[11]

More important, the American victory at Saratoga convinced France that an alliance with the Americans would be a good gamble. The French provided loans, a few troops, and, most importantly, naval support for the Americans. The French alliance also turned the rebellion into a wider war in which the British had to contend not only with the colonials but also with a French navy in the Caribbean and on the American coast. In the battle of Yorktown, the climactic campaign of the war, the vastness of America again defeated the British. In 1781 Lord Charles Cornwallis led an army through Virginia almost without opposition, then retreated to a peninsula at Yorktown. There he was besieged by George Washington's army and held in check by the French navy. Unable to escape or to get help, Cornwallis surrendered an entire British army. His defeat effectively ended the war. In the Treaty of Paris of 1783, the British recognized the independence of the United States and relinquished its territory from the Atlantic to the Mississippi.

The United States and the Soviet Union emerged as rival superpowers in the aftermath of World War II. During the , the two countries confronted each other indirectly in the arms race, the Space Race, propaganda campaigns, and proxy wars. In the 1960s, in large part due to the strength of the civil rights movement, another wave of social reforms was enacted which enforced the constitutional rights of voting and freedom of movement to African Americans. In the 1980s, Ronald Reagan's presidency realigned American politics towards reductions in taxes and regulations. The Cold War ended when the Soviet Union was dissolved in 1991, leaving the United States as the world's sole superpower. Foreign policy after the Cold War has often focused on many conflicts in the Middle East, especially after the September 11 attacks. Early in the 21st century, the United States experienced the Great Recession and the COVID-19 pandemic, which had a negative effect on communities.[12]

Summary

In conclusion, it should be said that the story of the United States begins with the thirteen colonies which by the late 18th century had 2.5 million people. In its struggle towards independence, the Declaration of Independence led to the American Revolution in 1776. Between the Revolution against Britain and the American Civil War in 1861, the young nation went through a myriad of storms, politically and socially, in addition to the significant progress it went through.

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